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Improvement of attitudes and skills using a MOOC about the basic science of climate change

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Education needs to be at the forefront of the efforts to mitigate and adapt to Climate Change (CC) effects. We have introduced the Climate Change Competence (C3) to provide a comprehensive route to include the topics of sustainability and CC into the curriculum. This paper analyses how different primary and secondary teachers can improve this competence using a Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) on the basic science of CC. While the improvement in knowledge is expected, we have observed important advances on abilities, and attitudes on CC which are also essential to teach about CC mitigation and adaptation. The present study used a pre-experimental design, with pre-and post-test measurements with a sample of 530 students. While the MOOC focuses on the Science of CC, the participants also advance in attitudes and abilities, revealing an important correlation between these three dimensions of competence. Also, the study reveals that the MOOC improves the C3 in all the participants, but it does in diverse ways for diverse groups.

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Introduction

The Climate Change crisis and the role of education. The publication of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's (IPCC) sixth assessment report has been a major step forward in the general acceptance of Climate Change (CC) as one of the most threatening environmental issues (IPCC, 2021). The unanimous call for action from climate experts and other international organisations has become more pressing. This "climate crisis" or "climate emergency" (IPCC, 2018) demands immediate actions, as indicated by the words of the UN secretary "CC is moving faster than we are" (IPCC, 2018). The changes in our current climate are evidenced through global observations of changing weather patterns, shifts in agricultural production, new health risks, and the general diminishing of natural resources. The severity of the climate crisis depends on our response and if this response is inadequate or insufficient, environmental degradation will continue and will result in a general deterioration of our livelihoods.

Based on accumulating scientific evidence, there is a clear consensus that the CC has an anthropogenic origin (IPCC, 2018). To avoid catastrophic consequences, societies must adopt a more sustainable way of living and a more climate-friendly model of economic growth. Public awareness is crucial to make the necessary behavioural changes (Borawska, 2020). Citizens need to realise that individual lifestyle choices (consumption and production practices) influence social, economic, and environmental development, i.e., humans are both cause and solution. The United Nations Development Programme's (UNDP) latest survey reveals that 64% of the people from 50 different countries believe that CC is a global emergency (UNDP, 2021). Despite the high awareness, nearly half of the people who identify CC as a global emergency do not demand urgent action, suggesting that more education is required, even for those who are already concerned about the issue (UNDP, 2021).

Previous studies have revealed that members of the public tend to have a partial, incomplete, and often poorly formed understanding of the issue (Corrochano et al., 2021; González-Gaudiano and Meira-Cartea, 2010; Tobler et al., 2012). There is evidence that a better understanding of CC science has positive consequences, leading to more awareness of environmental issues and a deeper sense of responsibility (Anderson, 2012). Therefore, this lack of understanding might be one of the barriers for citizens to transform their awareness into climate actions.

Education has the potential to fill this gap and help introduce positive changes. Investing in CC Education (CCE) is both ethical and cost-effective as its benefits will be shared among families and communities, multiplying its effect (Lawson et al., 2019; Mochizuki and Bryan, 2015; Peterson et al., 2019). Education can thereby play a key role in terms of public perception and draw the attention of a wide audience to the problem. To achieve the necessary social transformation, a comprehensive approach from the formal educational system is needed (Mochizuki and Bryan, 2015).

The Climate Change Competence. Climate Change is embedded with uncertainties, especially regarding the future, therefore, CCE should not only include relevant knowledge but also cultivate awareness and the necessary skills to navigate and manage through a rapidly changing and uncertain future. In this study, we use the previously proposed Climate Change Competence (C3) (Fuertes et al., 2020) as a strategy to implement CCE. The C3 fits into the key competence framework recommended by the European Union (EU) in May 2018, and it has many similarities to the recently introduced Green Competence (Bianchi et al., 2022). CCE must respond to the framework of competences that have

been designed specifically to prepare citizens to meet the challenges of this century (Delors, 1996). CC might be one of the most pressing issues of the twenty-first century and C3 offers a perfect framework to include the necessary knowledge and skills in the formal education system. Scientific knowledge, the first pillar of the lifelong learning strategy, is fundamental within the structure of C3 and includes all relevant concepts, facts, and already established theories needed to understand the essential principles of the Earth's climate system. This acquired knowledge is only considered useful when one can use it to achieve certain results. The skills and abilities necessary to put into practice the newly acquired concepts fall within the second pillar: learning to do. For the C3, these skills focus on the ability to make informed and responsible decisions about actions that may affect climate. CC is a global issue that requires a change in behaviour and attitude towards the natural environment. Some examples are changes in how we produce and consume energy, changes in how we produce and consume food, and awareness of the impact of human activities on natural resources. These items are included in C3 along its three dimensions, attitudes, abilities, and knowledge; this competence is a tool to include some of the most important methodologies and approaches proposed in CCE (Anderson, 2012; McCright et al., 2013; Monroe et al., 2019). C3 is also a guide to design educational interventions, itineraries for teachers and other education professionals, contents, and activities to increase awareness of the climate crisis, to improve the understanding of the problem, and acquire abilities towards mitigation and adaptation.

Another important aspect of the competence is its assessment. Together with C3, we have developed and validated an instrument to measure the evolution of C3 in students, teachers, and society in general (Ballegeer et al. [under revision](#)). The instrument consists of a questionnaire with Likert items which allow us to measure each of the dimensions of the competence as well as possible correlations between dimensions. Accurate measurements of the evolution of the competence, for example before and after educational interventions, allows us to assess the quality and effectiveness of the intervention. We can then quickly elaborate a tailored response and find ways to improve C3 optimising invested costs and resources. Efficiency in terms of time, cost and resources is crucial for CCE given the urgency of the issue, to tackle the climate crisis a large social transformation over a small period is needed.

MOOCs and Climate Change Education. To broaden the participation and to reach a wider audience, higher education institutions must pay attention to open and flexible ways of learning of this interdisciplinary educational challenge (Teixeira et al. 2012). In this sense, MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) have raised remarkable attention to teach different approaches to CC. Nearly 50 MOOCs, or other types of free eLearning courses, on CC have been released in the last decade for a worldwide audience, with an average duration of one month (Bacelar-Nicolau and Caeiro, 2020). These courses are designed to be taught to a large number of students at once, unlimited, and free of charge, allowing access to top-quality educational resources that otherwise may not be available to them financially and geographically. In the field of CCE, MOOCs are interesting tools because they favour the development of innovative experiences, they are up to date with the current scientific understanding and provide an interactive learning experience among participants and with the teachers, encouraging a collaboration between them (Ferrari et al., 2019; Otto, 2018). They create a sense of community that can contribute to raising awareness of

CC and its effects. MOOCs use visual and engaging imagery to capture the audience facilitating an effective transmission of fundamental concepts and messages. In this sense, Coelho et al. (2015) noticed that CC MOOCs should not be seen as repositories of educational materials, but as collaborative opportunities to promote interactive group work, with paced instruction, supported by quality and appropriate open education resources.

Several studies have highlighted that CC MOOCs stimulate learning and are able to increase the level of knowledge and awareness of their participants from an interdisciplinary perspective (Barteit et al., 2018; Ferrari et al., 2019; Otto et al., 2019). Other authors have also pointed out that MOOCs constitute promising tools to open education on CC literacy (Barteit et al., 2018; Otto et al., 2019), improving the social representation of CC, which may in turn trigger awareness and an effective mobilisation to address this important and urgent topic (Ferrari et al., 2019). In addition, MOOCs promote the social construction of this global problem (Burch and Harris, 2014), educate about the health impacts of CC (Barteit et al., 2018), improve science literacy awareness and discussion among the public (Shapiro et al., 2017) or boost climate literacy, especially when targeted to a specific group of people or in a specific setting (Otto et al., 2019). Nevertheless, despite these promising outcomes, MOOCs are still discussed in the literature. Some studies have shown that a relatively small number of students complete the MOOCs in which they enrolled (García-Peñalvo et al., 2018; Khalil and Ebner, 2014), and some authors have called attention to the fact that MOOCs neither accomplish to entice a considerable number of students from outside the higher education system nor those with a low prior knowledge about CC (Otto et al., 2019).

Factors influencing the Climate Change Competence. Previous research indicates that socio-demographic dimensions influence the population awareness and perception of the CC and are important predictors of environmental concern and climate action (Lee et al., 2015; McCright, 2010; Ortega-Egea et al., 2014; Weber, 2016). For example, some studies have revealed important gender-related differences, such as the fact that women are more likely than males to view CC as a serious threat and take action to address it (Weber, 2016). Younger adults tend to have more pro-environmental attitudes than older adults do, and they also think that CCE needs to be given more attention (Semenza et al., 2008; Weber, 2016). Results from high-income countries indicate that many perceive CC as distant both in time and space (Jones et al., 2017). However, studies show that people in Latin-American believe that CC is already happening and affecting their lives (Lee et al., 2015). All this information is especially relevant for CCE, because to promote action to tackle CC it is important to tailor pro-environmental messages more effectively to raise awareness among all groups in society. The broad audience of the MOOC can shed light on how C3 evolves in diverse groups with different socio-demographic characteristics and in different countries. For example, as the MOOC is geared towards teacher education, it serves specifically to analyse the impact it can have on teachers training, comparing teachers and other occupational groups (non-teachers in our study). The study will provide insights in both the structure of C3 and the efficiency of MOOCs as tools to increase climate literacy, awareness, and skills (attitudes and abilities) for CC mitigation and adaptation.

Our specific research questions are:

RQ1: Can a MOOC on basic science of Climate Change improve all dimensions of C3?

RQ2: Are there significant differences in the improvement of the C3 related to socio-demographic (teacher- no teacher, Spain-Latin America, age) characteristics?

Background and motivation and MOOC design. In this section we will frame the background and motivation for our study. Our research stems from the idea that basic knowledge is necessary for the social transformation required to address CC but is certainly not sufficient. The role of knowledge in determining changes in environmental behaviour is controversial, and has been questioned by some (Burgess et al., 1998; Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002; Lorenzoni et al., 2007) and defended by others (McNeal et al., 2017; Sadler et al., 2006). Knowledge does not in itself promote environmental action or the development of a pro-environmental behaviour. Nevertheless, knowledge should be recognised as one of the many prerequisites for the development of pro-environmental behaviours and competence leading to action. An accurate knowledge of the problem allows effective solutions and therefore it is essential. In this study, we investigate if teaching the basic science of CC can also improve some other aspects of the C3 such as abilities or attitudes or even promote climate action which, in principle, could be improved with other types of interventions.

CC is a complex topic and there is a big gap between the scientific literature and materials available to use in the schools or as a formative material for teachers. For these reasons we decided to design and produce a MOOC in Spanish on the basic science of CC made for primary and secondary teachers as well as the public with no scientific background. There are several characteristics of the MOOC format that are advantageous to improve the C3.

Global reach. As educational resources on CC are scarce in Spanish, a global reach means that they can become available everywhere with no cost. As the materials are designed under a creative commons licence, they can be reused by the teachers.

Updated and essential information. One of the most common problems that teachers encounter is the difficulty of filtering materials that are scientifically valid and relevant. Therefore, it is important to have a course for teachers and the public with up-to-date and well selected knowledge about CC.

An effective transmission of the message. The MOOC uses an informed but optimistic view about CC. It uses appropriate visual imagery which relates CC to social problems to capture the audience but avoids shocking and fearful representations of CC. We avoid long descriptions, and we use short videos, one for each section and five in each module.

The MOOC is organised around four basic questions. What is CC? What are its causes? What are its consequences? and What can we do? These simple questions were formulated to organise the complexity of the topic into six modules (Table 1) that cover the basic facts needed to understand CC and the importance of coordinated action.

The MOOC was designed and developed by Herrero et al. (2018) at the University of Salamanca and launched in 2018 through the MiriadaX platform. The MOOC focuses on the science of CC and explains the physical and chemical mechanisms responsible for the disruptions in the climate and its consequences. Instructors facilitated video presentations and provided interactive elements to ensure the interaction among students, encouraging the collaboration and discussions through online forums. Regarding our intervention as tutors of the MOOC, we become mere managers of the learning process, encouraging the students to progress in the course, answering doubts and ensuring that all of them can finish the course.

Learners can progress through the modules, doing the compulsory activities at their own pace. Some learners complete one module at a time, but we have seen that others do the

Table 1 The contents of MOOC.

Module	Description
Module 1: A changing climate. A scientific perspective. (10 h)	The questions: What is climate and how does it work? How is climate studied? are addressed in this module. There is also a brief review of the Earth's climate history and the relationship between climate and humans. Activities include characterisation of climate in the Holocene compared to previous geological periods.
Module 2: Evidence of Climate Change. (10 h).	The differences between climate variability and CC are explained in this module. The evidence of CC around the world is presented. Activities include the collection of news about extreme events.
Module 3. The functioning of Climate Change. (10 h).	Introduction to the physical-chemical processes that cause CC: The energy balance, the greenhouse effect, and the carbon cycle. Activities include reviewing the energy balance on earth.
Module 4. Human activity as a cause of Climate Change. (10 h).	In this module we review the impact of human activity on the planet, the origin of the greenhouse gas emissions. We also discuss the energy sector: basic concepts, consumption patterns and impact of the food sector. Activities include the study of emissions in different sectors.
Module 5: Future scenarios. (10 h).	The need for future predictions of the climate is highlighted. The fundamentals of current computational models are described, and the probable future scenarios are explained. Activities include the study of future climate scenarios,
Module 6: What can we do from education? (10 h).	The socio-economic aspects of CC are discussed in this module. Mitigation and adaptation strategies and the role of education are discussed. Activities include the discussion about individual and collective climate actions.

modules in blocks. We use a MOOC within the MiriadaX platform, part of the Telefónica Foundation, which is widely implemented in Spain and Latin America.

Materials and methods

To assess the development of competences around Climate Change or Sustainability using MOOCs is a complex task. It may require combining different assessments tailored to specific MOOC content and learner groups as competences are often context dependent. It may require simulating real-world scenarios (for example related to policy or climate actions) and it may require efficient and scalable methods to deal with large numbers of students as it usually occurs with MOOCs. In the recent literature there are examples of this type of assessment. The BECK project (Senevirathne et al., 2022) developed a framework for MOOC curricular development and assessment in climate change education, studying examples in two countries. A paper by D. Otto (Otto, 2018) and collaborators compares two different MOOCs to conclude that while MOOCs are a valuable tool for enhancing climate literacy, especially among those already engaged with the topic, they might not be useful for all students. A paper by Barteit (Barteit et al., 2018) and collaborators conclude that MOOCs may be an effective method for teaching and training global students on health and Climate Change and may be an enabler for equitable access to quality education.

To evaluate if the MOOC improves the C3 in this paper, we use a validated test to analyse the evolution of this competence, using a pre-experimental design without control group and with pre- and post-test measurements (Campbell and Stanley, 2015). The study was carried out with the participants of the second edition of the MOOC "Awareness and capacity building for Climate Change for Primary and Secondary school teachers."

The pre-post and pre-experimental design. The pre-test was carried out before the start of the MOOC and the post-test when students had completed the course. The final questionnaire was the same as the initial one. In addition, both responses were anonymous, thus they were treated as independent groups, using the Mann-Whitney *U* test. Following previous authors (Tabuenca et al., 2019; Vázquez et al., 2018; Yaşar and Polat, 2021), we define the universe of the sample (the students) and then we consider a first random sample of the respondents for the pretest and a second sample for the post-test. Even though the two subsamples are independent they belong to the same universe and therefore

the effect of the course can be measured (Alan et al., 2019; Kara and Kahraman, 2008).

MOOC design, knowledge based. The sample of this study consisted of people who took the MOOC during its second edition (March 2019). Although our MOOC was originally designed for teacher training it has been proved to be an effective tool to teach CC concepts to other sectors of society (Herrero et al., 2018). The MOOC has been made available for a wide audience, and therefore, it will allow us to assess the evolution of C3 in several social groups. 530 participants voluntarily answered the pre-test and 255 the post-test. The difference in the number of responses is due to the low completion rates of these types of courses, generally less than 10% (Ferrari-Lagos et al., 2020, García-Peñalvo et al., 2018; Khalil and Ebner, 2014). The pre-test participants in its majority were from Latin-America (58.9%) and Spain (38.1%), the other 3% came from Italy, Portugal, and Africa. Regarding their professions, 46.5% of the participants were teachers, 26.4% students and the remaining 27.1% non-teaching professionals. Regarding gender, 51.3% of the sample were females and 48.7% males, ages ranging from 20 to 77 (Mean = 36.1, SD = 13.6). Finally, most of the participants have a University Education (74.7%).

Instrument. The instrument used in this study is called Climate Change Competence (C3Q). This consists of a closed-ended 1–4 Likert-scale questionnaire with 36 items, which encompassed the 3 dimensions of C3 (knowledge, ability, and attitude) (Ballegeer et al.; under revision). Items of each dimension are randomly distributed through the survey. The McDonald's omega coefficient (McDonald, 1999) was used to estimate the reliability, due to the greater stability of its calculation with non-continuous data avoiding underestimates (Gadermann et al., 2012). The knowledge dimension measures interactions between scientific veracity of CC. The items were selected based on a study on scientific knowledge of CC developed in environmental education and psychology (Meira-Cartea et al., 2018). This dimension has 14 items (Appendix, Table A1), that assess the science of CC based on the following categories: "False", "Somewhat false", "Somewhat true" and "True". The dimension is composed of the following subdimensions: (1) biophysical processes (BPP); (2) causes (CAU); (3) consequences (CSQ); (4) adaptation and mitigation (A&M). The answers for this dimension were assessed using a

Likert scale with values ranging from 1 to 4, with 4 being the maximum value for correct statements.

The ability dimension of the competence was analysed with 9 items (Appendix, Table A2), distributed in three subdimensions: (1) Purchases (PUR); (2) transport (TRA); and (3) energy savings (ESA). These items inquire on how often the participants carry out activities related to CC mitigation in their daily life and were elaborated including items of previous studies (Bain et al., 2016; Gifford and Comeau, 2011; Whitmarsh and O'Neill, 2010). The items were assessed with a four-category Likert scale: "Never," "Occasionally," "Frequently" and "Always," corresponding with the values 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Finally, the attitude dimension included the following subdimensions: (1) trust per agent (TRU); (2) responsibility (RES); and (3) educational support (EDU). In the attitude dimension 13 items (Appendix, Table A3) were included, all adapted from the related literature (Boon, 2014; Feldman et al., 2012; IPCC, 2014a, 2014b; Karami et al., 2017; Reser et al., 2011). Participants were assessed with the next categories: "None," "Little," "Enough" and "Much," through the values 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. In all the dimensions, scores closer to 4 indicate higher levels of C3.

Data analysis. Initially, the evolution between the pre- and post-test was analysed through a descriptive exploration of the data (median, mean and standard deviation) using SPSS 26. Afterwards, determination of normality data was carried out to apply the nonparametric Mann–Whitney U t -test. If the results show a $p < 0.05$, the distribution of the criterion variable is significantly different when we compare pre-test and post-test or two groups. The level of significance used in all contrasts is analysed under 5%. To interpret its value, we add Glass Rank-biserial correlation as effect size (r). To quantify the magnitude of the difference between groups, values between 0.10 and 0.29, are considered as *minor differences*; 0.30 to 0.49 as *moderate differences*; and values greater than 0.50 as *large* (Cohen, 1988). Moreover, we use the Kruskal–Wallis test to compare three or more groups. We used the eta squared based on the H-statistic to determine effect size in this statistic. The interpretation values are: 0.01 to 0.05, *small effect*, 0.06 to 0.13 *moderate effect* and $> = 0.14$ *large effect*. To identify the group that presented a statistical difference we applied the Dunn multiple comparison test with Bonferroni adjustment.

Results

Evidence of validation of the instrument. The knowledge dimension had a McDonald's omega coefficient of 0.73, indicative of an adequate level of internal consistency. The confirmatory factor analysis showed that the four-factor model had a great fit ($\chi^2 = 139.65$, $df = 71$, $p < 0.021$). Analysis revealed three items loaded on factor 1 (biophysical processes) with r values ranging from 0.41 to 0.58, three items loaded on factor 2 (causes) with r values ranging from 0.40 to 0.52, four items loaded on factor 3 (consequences) with r values ranging from 0.37 to 0.53, four items loaded on factor 4 (adaptation and mitigation) with r values ranging from 0.36 to 0.56.

The ability dimension showed an acceptable value in the internal consistency of the dimension, whose value was 0.77. The three-factor model demonstrated excellent fit according to the goodness-of-fit test ($\chi^2 = 40.15$, $df = 24$, $p < 0.001$). It was found out that three items were loaded on every factor: factor 1 (purchases) with r values ranging from 0.46 to 0.54, factor 2 (transport) with r values ranging from 0.50 to 0.53 and factor 3 (energy saving) with r values ranging from 0.39 to 0.57.

The attitude dimension had an adequate value of the McDonald's omega coefficient (0.81), indicative of a high level of internal consistency. The confirmatory factor analysis showed that the three-factor model had an adequate fit ($\chi^2 = 73.95$, $df = 62$, $p < 0.142$). It was found out that five items loaded on factor 1 (trust for agent) with r values ranging from 0.55 to 0.71, five items loaded on factor 2 (responsibility) with r values ranging from 0.55 to 0.90 and factor 3 (educational support) with r values ranging from 0.66 to 0.78.

Finally, the entire scale was tested, presenting a adequate fit ($\chi^2 = 1150.44$, $df = 581$ $p < 0.001$), r values (knowledge: 0.71; ability: 0.68, and attitude: 0.87), and the McDonald's omega coefficient was 0.87, more details are summarised in Fig. 1.

Improvement of C3. First, we analysed whether our MOOC improves the dimensions of C3. To answer this, we used the nonparametric Mann–Whitney U t -test, where the independent variable was the course and dependent variables were every one of the subdimensions of C3. The results are summarised in Table 2.

A significant improvement in most sub-dimensions of C3 was observed. In the knowledge dimension, "biophysical processes" was the sub dimension with the highest improvement and "causes" showed least improvement. In the ability dimension, "purchases" and "transport" were the subdimensions with the best results, with moderate differences between pre- and post-test. Finally, "trust" and "educational support," both subdimensions of attitude, presented small improvements. Responsibility is the only sub dimension that did not show significant difference. However, this sub dimension has a p value close to 0.05.

These results for each of the dimensions are summarised in Table 3. The score of the dimensions was calculated using the mean scores of the subdimensions.

The difference between the average scores of the pre- and post-test has an effect size between 0.17 and 0.34. The results indicate that there are significant differences between pre-test and post-test, being post-test the one that presents a higher level of C3 in all dimensions.

Relation between improvement of C3 and sociodemographic characteristics. After verifying that our MOOC improves C3 in the whole sample, we study the effect of available socio-demographic characteristics in this improvement. We found significant differences between the participants that were teachers and non-teachers, Spanish versus Latin-American participants and between the different age groups of the participants.

When we compare the results of teachers versus non-teachers (Table 4), a larger improvement for the teachers was observed even though their initial score is lower compared to the rest. Conversely, the non-teacher group only showed improvement in the knowledge dimension.

Spanish and Latin-American participants improve in all dimensions. However, when we compare the pre-test of these regions, we observe statistical significance differences in the ability and attitude dimensions. Our data show that Latin-America participants obtained a median score of 3.22 and 3.78, significantly higher than median scores of Spanish participants, $Z = -4.17$ and -3.83 with $p < 0.001$, respectively for ability and attitude dimensions. It is worth noting that the completion rate was higher in Spain (61.9%) than in Latin-America (40.3%). The effect size values indicate that these differences were small (Table 5).

On the other hand, when we compare the post-test of both regions, statistically significant differences are only observed in the ability dimension. The effect size values indicate that these differences were moderate, close to being large.

Fig. 1 The factor structure of the C3Q. BPP Biophysical Processes, CAU Causes, CSQ Consequences, A_M Adaptation and Mitigation, PUR Purchases, TRA Transport, ESA Energy Savings, TRU trust per agent, RES Responsibility and EDU: Educational support.

Table 2 Comparative analysis between pre-test and post-test of C3 sub-dimensions.

Dimension	Subdimension	Test	n	Med	M	SD	U	Z	MWU p	r
Knowledge	Biophysical Processes	Pret	516	3.00	3.12	0.84	89122.0	-8.00	<0.001	-0.34
		Post	258	4.00	3.61	0.53				
	Causes	Pret	517	3.67	3.56	0.49	71716.0	-2.30	0.021	-0.10
		Post	253	4.00	3.64	0.42				
Ability	Consequences	Pret	517	3.00	3.03	0.72	74062.0	-2.72	0.007	-0.12
		Post	256	3.25	3.17	0.44				
	Adaptation and Mitigation	Pret	515	3.25	3.25	0.58	81845.0	-5.75	<0.001	-0.25
		Post	254	3.75	3.50	0.52				
Attitude	Purchases	Pret	530	3.00	3.06	0.65	85206.0	-5.69	<0.001	0.41
		Post	258	3.33	3.33	0.66				
	Transport	Pret	530	3.00	2.99	0.74	83065.5	-4.96	<0.001	0.37
		Post	258	3.33	3.26	0.72				
Attitude	Energy Saving	Pret	530	3.33	3.42	0.54	75318.5	-2.39	0.017	0.17
		Post	258	3.67	3.51	0.52				
	Trust	Pret	530	3.80	3.66	0.45	78152.5	-3.51	<0.001	0.24
		Post	258	4.00	3.76	0.37				
Responsibility	Pret	530	4.00	3.72	0.51	72914.5	-1.78	0.075	0.23	
	Post	258	4.00	3.82	0.35					
Educational Support	Pret	530	3.67	3.49	0.63	75636.0	-2.61	0.009	0.20	
	Post	258	4.00	3.61	0.59					

n sample size, Med median, M mean, SD standard deviation, U Mann-Whitney U (Test Statistic), Z Standardised Test Statistic, MWU p p-value of Mann-Whitney U, r Rank-Biserial Correlation (effect size).

Finally, we found significant differences between age groups related to the ability dimension. We applied a Kruskal-Wallis test because data is not presented normally. Based on the data of the age, we divided the sample into four age groups: (a) 20–34; (b) 35–49; (c) 50–64 and (d) ≥65; median scores in the ability dimension were 3.22, 3.11, 3.00 and 3.20, respectively (Table 6).

However, this trend changed for the group of ≥65. Ability scores were significantly different in this age group, $H(3) = 9.65$, $p = 0.022$. Dunn’s pairwise tests were carried out for the three pairs of groups. Pairwise comparisons using the Holm correction showed that both age groups, 35–49 and 50–64, presented lower ability scores ($p = 0.040$ and $p = 0.025$, respectively) compared to

Table 3 Comparative analysis between pre-test and post-test of C3 dimensions.

Dimension	Test	n	Med	M	SD	U	Z	MWU p	r
Knowledge	Pre	515	3.23	3.24	0.41	87295.0	-7.49	<0.001	-0.34
	Post	258	3.48	3.48	0.40				
Ability	Pre	530	3.22	3.16	0.49	84244.5	-5.31	<0.001	-0.24
	Post	258	3.44	3.37	0.52				
Attitude	Pret	530	3.70	3.62	0.39	80127.5	-3.98	<0.001	-0.17
	Post	258	3.87	3.73	0.32				

n sample size, Med median, M mean, SD standard deviation, U Mann-Whitney U (Test Statistic), Z Standardised Test Statistic, MWU p p-value of Mann-Whitney U, r Rank-Biserial Correlation (effect size).

Table 4 Comparative analysis of pre- and post-test in dimensions of C3 between teachers and non-teachers.

Dimension	Group	Teacher			No Teacher			U	Z	MWU p	r
		n	Med	M(SD)	n	Med	M(SD)				
Knowledge	Pre	226	3.19	3.22 (0.39)	127	3.56	3.51 (0.43)	18641.0	-6.23	<0.001	-0.41
	Post	117	3.27	3.27 (0.40)	68	3.41	3.49 (0.34)	5703.0	-3.69	<0.001	-0.32
Ability	Pre	240	3.11	3.12 (0.47)	137	3.44	3.37 (0.53)	18315.0	-4.22	<0.001	-0.28
	Post	120	3.22	3.21 (0.49)	70	3.28	3.31 (0.56)	5344.0	-1.35	0.177	-0.18
Attitude	Pre	240	3.67	3.62 (0.34)	137	3.89	3.77 (0.31)	18333.0	-4.28	<0.001	-0.27
	Post	120	3.78	3.64 (0.38)	70	3.82	3.71 (0.33)	5292.5	-1.24	0.214	-0.10

n sample size, Med median, M mean, SD standard deviation, U Mann-Whitney U (Test Statistic), Z Standardised Test Statistic, MWU p p-value of Mann-Whitney U, r Rank-Biserial Correlation (effect size).

Table 5 Comparative analysis of pre- and post-test in dimensions of C3 between Spain and Latin-America participants.

Dimension	Test	Spain			Latin-America			U	Z	MWU p	r
		n	Med	M (SD)	n	Med	M (SD)				
Knowledge	Pre	188	3.24	3.20 (0.42)	293	3.23	3.25 (0.40)	28492.5	-0.639	0.523	-0.04
	Post	126	3.46	3.46 (0.35)	118	3.57	3.52 (0.42)	8418.5	-1.79	0.073	-0.13
Ability	Pre	202	3.06	3.04 (0.48)	312	3.22	3.22 (0.48)	38347.5	-4.17	<0.001	-0.22
	Post	131	3.11	3.18 (0.52)	121	3.56	3.54 (0.44)	11048.0	-5.44	<0.001	-0.40
Attitude	Pre	202	3.62	3.54 (0.43)	312	3.78	3.67 (0.35)	37742.0	-3.83	<0.001	-0.20
	Post	131	3.80	3.71 (0.32)	121	3.89	3.74 (0.33)	8627.0	-1.25	0.213	-0.09

n sample size, Med median, M mean, SD standard deviation, U Mann-Whitney U (Test Statistic), Z Standardised Test Statistic, MWU p p-value of Mann-Whitney U, r Rank-Biserial Correlation (effect size).

the 20–34 age group, but with ≥65, there were no significant differences (Table 6). The effect size was small (20–34–35–49, $d = 0.20$ and 20–34–50–64, $d = 0.26$) for these differences. Figure 2 shows the results.

Discussion

Can a MOOC on CC improve all the dimensions of C3? A complete assessment of all the dimensions related to a MOOC about Climate Change is hard to develop, nevertheless, the tools that we have developed for the assessment and the corresponding analysis can help us to extract precise and valuable information about the possibilities that the MOOC format can provide in this important topic.

Our results reveal an improvement of all three dimensions of C3 for all the participants in the sample that we have studied. Similarly, Tabuenca et al., 2019 indicate that MOOCs are effective tools for encouraging environmental activism and creating locally relevant solutions to global issues.

One of the most important and surprising facts that we have found is how the attitudes and skills dimensions are developed

given that the MOOC is mostly about the basic science of Climate Change. Higher scores in the post-test of the knowledge dimension were expected as our MOOC focuses on improving basic understanding of climate science. Interestingly, the dimensions of ability and attitude also showed significant improvement among participants that completed our MOOC. These findings suggest that a better understanding of basic climate science has a positive impact on people’s skills and attitude towards CC. This indicates that the dimensions of the C3 are not decoupled, and knowledge can produce important effects on the other two dimensions.

Our data confirms the relation between knowledge and behaviour observed in CCE. Even though this is a complex and not fully understood relation, previous studies have found that knowledge about environmental problems leads to emotional involvement (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002) and stimulates pro-environmental behaviour (Dal et al., 2015; Otto et al., 2019; Pothitou et al., 2016).

A closer look into the subdimensions shows that, upon completion of our MOOC, participants show greater support towards the inclusion of CC in the educational system (sub

Table 6 Comparative analysis of ability by age.

Age	n	Med	Mean	SD	Coefficient of variation	H	df	KWHp
20-34	246	3.22	3.22	0.48	0.15	9.65	3	0.02
35-49	148	3.11	3.12	0.46	0.15			
50-64	85	3.00	3.09	0.51	0.16			
65	18	3.22	3.20	0.54	0.17			

Dunn's Post Hoc Comparisons - Age

Comparison	z	Wi	Wj	p	pHolm	Cohen's d
20-34-35-49	2.48	268.46	231.51	2.14 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.04	0.20
20-34-50-64	2.64	268.46	220.75	8.18 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.02	0.26
20-34-+65	0.23	268.46	260.28	0.82	1	0.04
35-49-50-64	0.55	231.51	220.75	0.58	1	0.06
35-49-+65	-0.8	231.51	260.28	0.42	1	-0.16
50-64-+65	-1.06	220.75	260.28	0.29	1	-0.23

n sample size, Med median, M mean, SD standard deviation, H Kruskal-Wallis H (Test Statistic), df degree free, KWH p p value of Kruskal-Wallis H, Z Standardised Test Statistic, Wi mean ranking of first group, Wj mean rankings of second group, Cohen's D = effect size

Fig. 2 Mean scores between different age groups on the ability dimension. The age groups 20-34 and 65-79 were not significantly different according to the Kruskal-Wallis Test and Dunn's Multiple Comparison's Test.

dimension educational support). This is an encouraging result given that CCE is considered a cost-effective strategy to combat the climate crisis, although a formal approach is yet to be established. Our MOOC has had a positive impact on participants' attitude towards CCE. Our results reaffirm the importance of education to tackle the climate crisis and support the inclusion of C3 into the CCE.

Differences in the improvement of C3 related to socio-demographic characteristics. Investing in education to fight CC is one of the most cost-effective tools as its benefits will be shared by the whole educational community (Lawson et al., 2019; Mochizuki and Bryan, 2015; Peterson et al., 2019). Primary and secondary teachers will be responsible for educating the future generations and choosing the best resources and methodologies is of vital importance for their training. In this way, the fact that the MOOC was available for the public was a good opportunity to compare the impact of training on the foundations of CC on the evolution of the dimensions of C3 between teachers and other social groups (non-teachers in our study).

The results obtained show that our MOOC is an efficient tool to train teachers in CC. Teachers improve in the post-test in the three dimensions of C3, however, non-teachers only improve in the knowledge component but not in the ability and attitude. These results could be explained by the initial interest in the topic and because teachers are more familiar with this kind of courses in their professional development and therefore make a better use of the contents and resources provided in MOOCs.

Previous studies in the literature can help us to provide context to these results: Many teachers have a lack of confidence about their personal knowledge of CC (Oversby, 2015). Most of them have an oversimplified view of the phenomenon and doubts about the credibility of scientific hypotheses (Rudolph, 2007). One of the biggest problems of training teachers about CC is the lack of connection between the different sciences involved in the issue (Berger, 2015; Oversby, 2015). The MOOC might prove a helpful solution to these problems as it integrates contents of several disciplines, including natural sciences (e.g., physics, chemistry, biology, or geology) and social sciences and highlights the connection between those. The rigid structure of national

education curriculums, very compartmentalised, represent an important barrier for CCE (Schreiner et al., 2005) and this type of MOOCs can help to reduce this barrier as it can be easily adapted and freely disseminated among the whole education community, the information is easy to re-edit and update, it permits an effective transmission of the message and allows quick and dynamic feedback with the participants.

A notable and consistent improvement after instruction can be seen along the three dimensions of C3 between Spanish and Latin-American participants (Table 4), confirming that MOOCs are powerful educational tools to promote CCE without any geographical barrier. Latin-American participants exhibit higher scores in all dimensions of C3, both in the pre- and post-test results. Pre-test results exhibit significant differences in the ability and attitude dimensions of C3 between both groups, whereas post-test results indicate that there is a statistically significant difference only in the ability dimension.

As expected, due to the design of the course, highest improvement was noted in the knowledge dimension both in Spanish and Latin-American students (Table 4). The knowledge about CC was similar in both groups before instruction and their improvement was also remarkably similar. In contrast with the results of the knowledge dimension, Latin-American participants obtained better results in the ability and attitude dimensions before and after taking the course, and their improvement in the ability dimension was considerable. This suggests that Latin-American participants are more concerned about some behavioural and positional features of CC than Spanish participants, and it also suggests that they are more likely to change their daily actions (or at least, they proclaim that they will exert more personal effort to protect the environment) after some educational intervention. Important levels of CC concern have also been reported in previous studies in Latin-America (Evans and Zechmeister, 2018) and is especially evident in local peasant and indigenous communities (Forero et al., 2014). This is probably because in Latin-America the impacts of CC are significant and already manifested in several territories (Azócar et al., 2021).

Regarding the influence of the participants' age in the development of C3, our data reveals a meaningful relationship between age and scores in the ability dimension. Participants of the age groups 20–34 and 65–79 have more appropriate skills to face the climate crisis. In the youngest age group, we find a population extraordinarily aware of the issue, connected through social networks and that have echoed the latest social movements developed in their countries collecting ideas, proposals and witnessing the COP Climate Summits organised by the UN since 1992.

The age group over 65 could reflect the first wave of environmental awareness that occurred in the 70s and 80s. People of this age were the first generation to worry about environmental issues through movements such as Ecologists in Action in Spain, Greenpeace, WWF/Adena, Friends of the Earth or SEO/Birdlife worldwide. These social movements were founded in the 70s, around the time of the UN Declaration of Stockholm of 1972, the first document in history on an international environmental law. Although the sample size in this age range is small, these results could be explained on the basis that awareness and importance of these environmental issues were remarkably high in these two indifferent decades. Further research on these age groups could help to test whether this is the case.

Conclusions and limitations

The focus of our study is the impact of a MOOC about the foundations of CC on C3 and it demonstrates that participants

improve the three dimensions of C3: knowledge, ability, and attitude. Participating in the MOOC improved knowledge and competencies to deal with the current climate crisis, indicating that the core message of the MOOC has been successfully conveyed to the students. These results suggest that investing resources and efforts to explain the basics of CC helps to produce an increase in abilities and attitude towards CC in people and potentially can trigger a more pro-environmental attitude. In effect, our study highlights the importance and the necessity of understanding CC to promote climate action.

Although the importance of education in this task has been recognised by international organisations, there is no formal approach established by governments. From our point of view, and according to many of the participants of the MOOC, the inclusion of C3 in the formal educational system could be a good strategy to combat CC. These findings also confirm that the C3 could be a good vehicle to advance the CCE and to respond to the current climate crisis in an appropriate manner which includes knowledge, practical skills, ethical values, attitudes, etc. and achieve effective action in the students of the MOOC.

Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample influence the development of C3. Teachers show lower values in the pre-test than non-teachers, but their improvement is bigger. In CCE it is essential to understand the connection among all disciplines of this global problem and our MOOC integrates contents of environmental and social sciences and highlights the connection between different disciplines, which sometimes is difficult to see. Teachers are more used to enrolling in these kinds of courses and for this reason they make better use of the contents and resources of the MOOCs which could have facilitated their understanding of these complicated concepts. On the other hand, Latin-American participants exhibit higher scores in all dimensions of C3 than Spanish participants, due to differences in the official curricula: Latin-America is more strongly affected by CC and therefore their official curricula include more aspects of this problem. Finally, the age of participants also influences the development of C3. The age groups 20–34 and 60+ years old are inclined to behave more environmentally friendly. Interestingly, these two groups could be influenced by two periods in the recent history of our society: the birth of environmental associations in the 70ths and the current climate emergency. These could make the oldest and the youngest participants in our study more aware about environmental problems.

Our findings have limitations, especially in terms of generalisation of the conclusions as we examined only a small sector of society, especially the case for the 65+ age group. In addition, although the results between pre- and post-test are significant, the fact that they were treated as independent groups, needs to be taken in consideration when interpreting the results. Moreover, the studied sample consists of students who voluntarily enrolled in a course of CC, and this may probably influence their predisposition, awareness, and general knowledge of the problem. Therefore, further research is needed especially with a broader scope of samples to obtain more precise findings. Future studies should also consider evaluating other knowledge-based interventions in addition to the MOOCs to explore the evolution of C3. In addition, as C3 aims to raise awareness and mobilise individuals for climate action, it would be interesting to consider conducting longitudinal studies to analyse the impact of the C3 in people's daily lives.

Appendix

Tables A1–A3

Table A1 Knowledge Dimension of C3.

No.	Subdimension	Item
1	BPP	The greenhouse effect is a natural phenomenon.
2		CO2 is a natural component of the atmosphere.
3		If it were not the greenhouse effect, there would be no life as we know it.
4	CAU	Climate change is caused by human activity.
5		There is scientific consensus when considering human activity as the main cause of climate change.
6	CSQ	Every time coal, oil or gas is used, we contribute to climate change.
7		Climate change is a consequence of the hole in the ozone layer.
8		The CO2 causes the destruction of the ozone layer.
9		Climate change will increase the number of earthquakes and tsunamis.
10		The rising temperatures will affect all regions of the planet alike.
11		The increase in meat consumption contributes to climate change.
12	A&M	If we stop emitting greenhouse gases, we will be less vulnerable to climate change.
13		Climate change would be reduced if we planted more trees.
14		Replacing private transport by the public is one of the most effective measures to address climate change.

BPP Biophysical Processes, CAU Causes, CSQ Consequences, A&M Adaptation and Mitigation.

Table A2 Ability Dimension of C3.

No.	Subdimension	Item
1	PUR	I choose fruits and vegetables produced in my country over those of foreign origin
2		I buy local and seasonal products
3		I buy organic farming or livestock products
4	TRA	I walk or use my bike as a daily means of transportation.
5		I use carpooling or public transportation.
6	ESA	I reduce the use of the car.
7		Consumption less electricity
8		I turn off lights and electrical appliances when I'm not using them
9		I use less heating

PUR Purchases, TRA Transport, ESA Energy Savings.

Table A3 Attitude dimension of C3.

No.	Subdimension	Item
1	TRU	It indicates the level of confidence in the information on CC provided by the following agents
2		Teachers
3		Ecologist
4		UN
5		Scientists
6	RES	Media
7		Indicate the degree of responsibility of the following levels of organisation in dealing with climate change
8		International
9		National
10	EDU	Regional
11		Local
12		Individual
13		Please indicate your level of agreement on the following issues
		A new key competence should be created specifically for climate change.
		There should be a specific subject on climate change.
		Key competencies should include climate change.

TRU Trust per Agent, RES Responsibility and EDU: Contribution through Education.

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Author contributions

Conceptualisation: C.R., methodology: C.R., E.F., formal analysis: E.F., investigation: A.-M.B.: D.C., M.A.F., P.H., L.D., S.A.-S.; data curation: E.F; writing—original draft preparation: C.R., writing—review and editing: A.-M.B., D.C., L.D., S.A.-S., visualisation: E.F.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethical approval

This study was performed in line with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Approval was granted by the Ethics Committee of University of Salamanca under the research project “Competencia climática en alumnado de Educación Primaria, Secundaria y universidad” n° de registro 925, Spain.

Informed consent

Informed consent was duly acquired from all participants and/or their legal guardians prior to their involvement in the study. This consent was systematically obtained at the outset of the electronic questionnaire, which each participant acknowledged and agreed to. At this juncture, a comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the questionnaire and the overarching objectives of the research was provided to the participants, ensuring clarity and transparency in the study’s intent and methodology.

Additional information

Supplementary information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03139-6>.

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